

Synthesis of Indoles from Some Ortho-Hydroxy Halogenated Acetophenones

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Fischer *et al.*¹⁻⁴ synthesized 2-phenyl indoles by cyclising phenyl hydrazones of different acetophenones employing acid condensing agents such as anhydrous zinc chloride, although the cyclisation of the phenyl hydrazone of 4-hydroxy 2,6-dibromo acetophenone in order to synthesise the corresponding indole could not be successful⁵. The authors have cyclised by Fischer's indole synthesis a number of phenyl hydrazones of some hydroxy and halogen substituted acetophenones which were synthesized through Fries migration. In the present communication the synthesis of 2-phenyl indoles from the phenyl hydrazones of 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro, 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro, 2-hydroxy-5-bromo, 2-hydroxy-3,5-dibromo and 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-methyl acetophenones, has been described. The influence of the presence of hydroxy, halogens, and methyl substituents in the benzene nucleus of acetophenones on the yields of 2-phenyl indoles has also been discussed.

1. *Synthesis of phenyl hydrazones of o-hydroxy halogenated acetophenones* : Substituted phenyl acetates were obtained from the corresponding phenols by usual methods and they were submitted to migration. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 moles) was added to halogen substituted phenyl acetate (1 mole) in small portions with vigorous stirring. The mixture was heated on water bath till the contents got liquified. It was then heated on oil bath at 140-165° for about 1 hr. The product was cooled and decomposed with dil. hydrochloric acid (1.5 moles) containing ice. On steam distillation, the corresponding o-hydroxy halogenated acetophenones were obtained. They were crystallized from alcohol. Phenyl hydrazones were synthesized by heating equimolecular alcoholic solutions of corresponding substituted acetophenones and phenyl hydrazine for about half an hour.

2. *Synthesis of indoles* : o-Hydroxy halogenated acetophenone phenyl hydrazone (1.2 moles) and anhydrous zinc chloride (4 moles) were thoroughly mixed and heated at 135-145° for 3 hrs on an oil bath. The contents were thoroughly cooled. The cold hard mass thus obtained was digested with hydrochloric acid containing ice. The indoles, which precipitated out, were filtered, washed with cold water and finally crystallized from alcohol. The characteristics of indoles synthesized have been described in Table 1.

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1. Fischer and Jourden, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2241.
2. Hes and Fischer, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 559.
3. Schmidt and Fischer., *Ber.*, 1886, **21**, 1071.
4. Fischer, *Ann.*, 1886, **236**; 133.
5. Karezynski and Kierzch (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE 1
Synthesis of Indoles from the Phenyl Hydrazones

Sl. No.	Phenyl hydrazones of 2-hydroxy	Indole	Colour	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	% Halogen	
							Reqd.	Found
1.	5-Chloro acetophenone	2(2-hydroxy 5-chloro phenyl)	Brown	160	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NOCl	14.50	13.54
2.	5-Bromo acetophenone	2(2-hydroxy 5-bromo phenyl)	Brown	170	45	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ NOBr	27.77	27.10
3.	3-Bromo, 5-chloro acetophenone	2(2-hydroxy 3-bromo 5-chloro phenyl)	Buff	195	35	C ₁₄ H ₉ NOClBr	35.81	35.03
4.	3-Chloro, 5-bromo acetophenone	2(2-hydroxy 3-chloro 5-bromo phenyl)	Creamy	201	35	C ₁₄ H ₉ NOClBr	35.81	35.42
5.	3,5-Dibromo acetophenone	2(2-hydroxy 3,5-dibromo phenyl)	—	Charring		C ₁₄ H ₉ NOBr ₂	43.32	—
6.	3-Bromo, 5-methylacetophenone	2(2-hydroxy 3-bromo, 5-methyl phenyl)	Greenish	192	50	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ NOBr	25.42	25.20

Melting point uncorrected.

It is quite interesting to note that the presence of various substituents in the benzene nucleus of the acetophenones exerts much influence on the cyclisation of the phenyl hydrazones, and the yield of the indoles. When only one halogen atom is present along with one hydroxyl group in the ortho-position, the yield of the indole obtained is approximately 40–50% of the theoretical value. When 2 halogen atoms are present along with one hydroxyl group in the *o*-position, the yield is approximately 30–35% of the theoretical value. If the two halogen atoms present are bromine atoms, considerable charring takes place and the indole synthesis is greatly hindered.

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